

CHARACTERISATION OF HEXTOOL COMPOSITE FOR RTM MOULDS

K.Szymanska¹, M. Salvia¹

¹Laboratoire de Tribologie et de Dynamique des Systèmes, Ecole Centrale de Lyon, Ecully

michelle.salvia@ec-lyon.fr

katarzyna.szymanska@ec-lyon.fr

Summary

HexTOOL composite is a new mould solution for the manufacture of aerospace components. It needs to be properly characterized in term of its thermomechanical behaviour for which it can be subjected during manufacturing of composites. The studies were divided in three parts: raw material behaviour, thermo-mechanical tests and durability investigation.

1. Introduction

The use of composite materials in aeronautic industries continues to increase. The manufacturing of composite parts involves complex cure process and appropriate tools. There are different techniques for composites moulding. The resin transfer moulding (RTM) process is widely applied to elaborate composite parts. HexTOOL composite (bismaleimide resin (BMI) /carbon fibre) supplied by Hexcel is a new mould solution for the manufacture of aerospace components. It is an alternative to conventional metallic moulds. Its lightweight and the ability to machine tool surface without distortion due to its specific architecture (randomly layered strips of unidirectional carbon fibre) allow the manufacture of moulds with complex shapes and high tolerance. The tool structure is subjected to various loading and temperature cycles during the manufacturing process of composite units. So, there is a great need for the characterisation of HexTOOL composite and its BMI matrix.

2. Materials and methods

This work will be divided in three sections:

- 1) Cure behaviour of raw materials and cure kinetics models
- 2) Thermo-mechanical characterization of cured materials coupled with SEM monitoring and AE damage investigation.
- 3) Creep tests and creep modelling of cured composite

2.1. Cure tests on raw materials

The materials under investigation used for cure tests were raw BMI resin and its carbon fibre reinforced prepreg.

The reactivity and performance of tested materials during cure were investigated by two major techniques: Differential Scanning Calorimetry and Dynamical Mechanical Analysis. These two complementary procedures make possible to fully describe the thermo-chemical-mechanical phenomena occurring in tested sample during specified thermal program.

The DSC thermograms show the physical and chemical changes arising in curing material. From the other hand DMA test reveals the visco-elastic character of studied sample by measuring its mechanical response to a sinusoidal oscillatory force.

The calorimetric measures were performed through dynamical and isothermal runs. Each thermal program was divided in two steps. The first dynamic run was carried out with specified heating rate, in the range of 0.5°C/min - 20°C/min from -30°C to 350°C. The second dynamic run was achieved with 10°C/min from 25°C to 400°C.

The isothermal programs were realized also in two steps. The first runs were made isothermally at specified temperature in the range from 150°C to 250°C during fixed amount of time (5min-7hours). The second sweep for this method was performed by

sample heating from -30°C to 400°C with heating rate of 10°C/min.

The DMA measurements were performed mainly by dynamic runs due to specification of test apparatus heating mode. The heating rates used in this analysis were situated in the range between 1°C/min to 3°C/min. The samples were heated from 25°C to 350°C. The frequencies were chosen in the range of 0,1Hz - 10Hz.

2.2. Thermo-mechanical characterization of cured materials

The materials used, for thermo-mechanical characterization, were: the cured BMI resin and its carbon fibre reinforced HexTOOL.

For this type of characterization different methods of investigations were undertaken. Firstly, the DSC and DMA analysis were performed to defined chemical and thermo-mechanical state of commercially fabricated materials. The tests were carried out in dynamical mode with heating rate of 10°C/min for DSC and 1°C/min for DMA.

The monotonic 3-point bending tests coupled with AE (acoustic emission) monitoring were accomplished in aim to find the origins of damage and to monitor the crack propagation in BMI matrix and in its carbon fibre reinforced composite at 23°C.

2.3. Durability (creep) studies on HexTOOL composite

The creep behaviour was studied on commercially cured HexTOOL composite by 3-point bending test in the thermally controlled hermetic chamber. The monitoring of time and temperature dependent durability behaviour was achieved through isothermal tests at temperature range of 25°C-200°C by applying different load levels (20%-60% of ultimate flexural strength in RT) during 6h.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. DSC Cure tests on raw materials

3.1.1 Dynamical experimental results

The DSC thermograms were obtained by Mettler Toledo DSC1 instrument. Fig.1. shows the raw BMI dynamical DSC data at first heating run for three heating rates (5°C/min, 10°C/min and 15°C/min). The respective conversion curves for both materials at all used heating rates were developed in the aim to

calculate activated energy for MFK (Model Free Kinetics) and N-order models.

Fig.1. First dynamic runs for a) raw BMI resin and b) HexTOOL prepreg at 3 heating rates (3°C/min, 5°C/min, 10°C/min);

The both, T_{g0} (glass transition temperature of uncured material) and $T_{g\infty}$ (glass transition temperature of fully cured material), are heating rate dependent. T_{g0} can be estimated at about 5°C, and $T_{g\infty}$ is about 300°C for BMI resin. The total heat flow of cure reaction (ΔH_{tot}) for BMI resin is about 300 J/g, and slightly lower for prepreg composite. These results are consistent with other studies [1]. This difference can be explained by a slowdown of polymerization by restrict in mobility of molecules in the presence of carbon fibres.

3.1.2 Isothermal experimental results

The classic isothermal tests for BMI resin and HexTOOL prepreg were carried out in the range of temperatures: 150°C-250°C and for at least four duration times. The respective second dynamic runs were also obtained in the aim to estimate the cure rate and T_g (glass transition) of not fully cured materials.

There are many authors who confirm the relationships between T_g and cure extent of

thermosetting polymers following Di Benedetto equation [2, 3]. The original DiBenedetto equation was modified by Pascault to calculate the reaction extent x by determining the T_g for a different high crosslinked network, as follows:

$$\frac{T_g - T_{g_0}}{T_{g_\infty} - T_{g_0}} = \frac{\lambda x}{1 - (1 - \lambda)x} \quad (1)$$

Where T_g is the glass transition temperature of the sample after isothermal cure for a specified cure time. λ is the ratio of, ΔC_{p_∞} , for the fully cured material to ΔC_{p_0} of uncured material. The results of series of isothermal analyses for BMI resin fulfilled the DiBenedetto modelling represented by following equation:

$$T_g = 5,5 + \left(\frac{95,2\alpha}{1 - (0,68\alpha)} \right) \quad (2)$$

3.2 Cure kinetics

The thermosets cure kinetic modelling was, since fifty years, the subject of numerous studies [4]. The different models were used to approximate the curing behaviour of reactive systems. The classically used epoxy mixtures were, till now, well defined by Bailleul Model, Borchard Daniels Model or by Ozawa Flynn approach. The BMI industrial mixtures are frequently very complex. They contain softeners, additives and other elements which may modify the cure behaviour in term of rapidity or by changing the chemical nature of cure mechanism itself (diffusion-controlled or auto-catalytic one). The experimental dynamical curves were simulated by ASTM method, MFK analysis, N-order approach and Bailleul Model. The most accurate results were obtained for two cases: MFK and N-order modelling. The other estimations cannot fully define the complexity of cure phenomena and reactivity of studied BMI mixture. The kinetic triplet was determined and the simulations are in accordance to the experimental results.

The MFK model defines the cure kinetics with presented equation [5]:

$$\beta \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k_a \exp\left(-\frac{E(\alpha)}{RT}\right) f(\alpha) \quad (3)$$

BMI resin dynamical DSC results and its MFK simulations are presented in Fig.2.

Fig.2. First dynamic experimental sweep for raw BMI resin 3 heating rates (5°C/min, 10°C/min, 15°C/min) and its MFK simulations

The activation energy evolution was also calculated (Fig.3).

Fig.3. Apparent activation energy vs. cure rate for BMI resin calculated by MFK model.

The N-order approach is defined by the expressions showed above:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(1 - \alpha)^n \quad (4)$$

$$k = k_a \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k_a \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (6)$$

The comparison of N-order simulation and experimental results for BMI resin is showed in Fig.4.

Fig.4. First dynamic experimental runs for raw BMI resin at 3 heating rates (5°C/min, 10°C/min, 15°C/min) and N-order simulations;

3.3. DMA cure analysis

The cure behaviour of investigated materials was equally evaluated by shear DMA tests, through dynamical sweeps. The gel times and the vitrification phenomenon for curing samples (raw BMI resin) were detected. Fig.5. displays the evolution of G' and $\tan \delta$ for BMI resin in the range of temperatures: 25°C - 350°C for three frequencies (0, 1; 1 and 10Hz)

Fig.5. G' , $\tan \delta$ evolution vs temperature during BMI dynamic curing at 1°C/min.

The phenomenon of vitrification is distinctly marked in $\tan \delta$ curve evolution by frequency dependence. The gel time is approximately at about 160°C for 1°C/min heating rate. It was proved that the cure rate at this time is about 45%. It can be also noted the increase of G' . This phenomenon can be associated with and a phase separation which is equally reflected in viscosity evolution.

3.4. Thermo-mechanical characterization of cured materials

3.4.1. DSC and DMA analysis

The industrially cured BMI resin and HexTOOL composite were subjected to DSC and DMA analysis. The DSC dynamical thermograms, of both materials, heated at 1°C/min from 100-350°C are presented in Fig.6

Fig.6. DSC thermograms for BMI resin and HexTOOL composite.

The both thermograms present a slight rise of heat flow in the range of temperatures from 100°C to 260°C. This small increase in heat flow can be due to the residual cure reaction. It must be noted that both materials are not fully cured after industrial manufacturing process. For the used applications this cure rate is satisfactorily high, at about 95%. However, this phenomenon can be clearly demonstrated by DMA analysis on BMI (Fig. 7). The DMA dynamical were performed at 1°C/min heating. In fact, the $\tan \delta$ shows a double peak in the α -relaxation range. This residual reticulation is erased by a second dynamic step.

Fig.7. E' and $\tan \delta$ of BMI resin at first (high) and second (bottom) DMA heating run.

3.4.2 Monotonic micro 3-point bending tests

The three point bending tests were carried out in the SEM chamber using the micro monotonic 3-point bending apparatus. The loading rate was 2mm/min. The respective images of damage evolution were captured during test. Fig.8 shows the BMI and HexTOOL composite force vs. deflexion evolutions. The corresponding SEM image of damage monitoring is presented in Fig. 10.

Fig.8. Curve of force vs. deflexion during monotonic 3-point bending test for BMI and HexTOOL.

The average value of apparent modulus for BMI resin is about 4 GPa ($\pm 5\%$) and 30 GPa ($\pm 40\%$) for HexTOOL composite. This difference in test dispersion is related to a specific local architecture of tested composite. Even if the final damages are similar for all the samples the crack propagation and its origins depend on local sample architecture. The final rupture of material is preceded by a detachment of superficial strip layer of carbon fibres (see Fig.9).

Fig.9. Final stage of damage for HexTOOL composite

During SEM observation it can be proved that even if origins of damage are related with cracks in the matrix, the propagation is not

catastrophic for HexTOOL composite and it can be stopped by a fibre bundle. From this time the fibres for which the orientation is normal to crack opening are pulled out. The good adhesion matrix –fibres and the fibre random dispersion make HexTOOL composite very resistant material. The AE analysis of damage was also used in the aim to monitor the appearance of different damage types in tested composite. It can be noted that the main damage is preceded by a few low amplitude events due to the matrix cracks. The detachment of fibre package is observed as succeeding salves of low (matrix cracks), average (pull-out) and high amplitude (fibre cracks).

In the case of BMI resin it can be noted that the final failure is brittle. Nevertheless during the 3-point bending test, high number of small dispersed cracks can be observed due to the presence of TP that leads to an improvement in toughness. The SEM images of BMI damage are given in Fig.10.

Fig.10. SEM micrographs of BMI matrix during and after 3-point bending test.

3.4.3. Durability studies on cured HexTOOL composite

The creep tests were performed in a 3-point bending mode. HexTOOL composite, as a new mould solution for manufacturing composite parts, has to sustain the working temperature at about 200°C and continues loading during several hundred cycles. This composite was tested in four different temperatures (50°C, 100°C, 150°C, 200°C) and two loadings (40%, 60% of ultimate flexural strength). Fig. 11 illustrates the compliance curves vs. time for both loadings.

Fig.11. Curve of creep compliance vs. log time for HexTOOL composite for 40% and 60% of flexural ultimate strength at 4 different temperatures.

During the first ten minutes of constant loading application the compliance evolutions, are quite similar for all cases. The slight differences can be noted for the highest temperature 200°C. The second part of compliance curves presents a strongly divergent behaviour. The more temperature and load increase, the more non linearity of HexTOOL creep is pronounced. The first crack apparition is noted in the samples tested at 200°C and at 60% of ultimate load. The non linearity of creep behaviour increases with high temperature and high load levels. The crucial thermal boundary which activates the different creep behaviour is located between 100°C and 150°C. This is confirmed by a dynamical creep tests carried out with 2°C/min heating rate for both loads.

4. Conclusions

The HexTOOL composite and its BMI matrix were completely characterized. The cure kinetics of tested resin and its prepreg composite were estimated and seem to correlate with MFK and N-order model. The characteristic phenomena observed during cure were clearly visualized.

In addition the specific architecture of tested material was pointed out through 3-point bending tests coupled with SEM observations.

The damage origins for both BMI resin and HexTOOL composite were investigated by microscopic observations and AE analysis.

The creep behaviour of HexTOOL composite was studied and proved to be strongly related with local architecture of tested material.

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References

- [1] Zhansheng Guo, Shanyi Du, Boming Zhang, Zhanjun Wu "Cure Kinetics of T700/BMI Prepreg Used for Advanced Thermoset Composite" *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, Vol.97, Issue 6, p. 2175–2510
- [2] S.L. Simon "Cure and properties of thermosetting polymeric systems Epoxy/Amine and dicyanate ester/polycyanurate materials. Ph.D. Thesis: University, New Jersey, 1992, p.292
- [3] C.Texter, M.Taha, A.Mazzouz, and J.P.Pascault "Kinetic and rheological relationships of dicyanate ester polycondensation for the resin transfer moulding process", *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 1997, Vol 37, No7, p. 1238-1245
- [4] J. P. Pascault, H.Sauterau, J.Verdu, and R.J.J.Williams "Thermosetting Polymers" MarcelDekker, In., Swiss, 2002.
- [5] Jinwu Wang, Marie-Pierre G. Laborie, Michael P. Wolcott Comparison of model-free kinetic methods for modeling the cure kinetics of commercial phenolformaldehyde resins, *Thermochimica Acta*, 2005, Vol. 439, p. 68–73